

**PROCEEDINGS OF ELT UPGRADES 2019:
A FOCUS ON METHODOLOGY**

Ho Chi Minh City
University of Food Industry

PROCEEDINGS OF ELT UPGRADES 2019: **A FOCUS ON** **METHODOLOGY**

SCIENCE AND TECHNICS PUBLISHING HOUSE

PROCEEDINGS OF ELT UPGRADES 2019: A FOCUS ON METHODOLOGY

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PROCEEDINGS OF ELT UPGRADES 2019: A FOCUS ON METHODOLOGY

Time: 8.00 – 11.40 December 25th, 2019 - Venue: Lecture Hall C

HO CHI MINH CITY UNIVERSITY OF FOOD INDUSTRY

Website: www.eltforum.info
Email: elt.forum@cntp.edu.vn
140 Le Trong Tan Street, Tay Thanh Ward,
Tan Phu District, Ho Chi Minh City

8.00 – 8.15

Registration

08.15 – 8.30	WELCOME SPEECH					
	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Nguyen Xuan Hoan Chair of the Organizing Committee of National ELT Upgrades Conference 2019					

08.30 – 09.30	Keynote Speaker - Assoc. Prof. Dr. Nguyen Ngoc Vu Vice President – Hoa Sen university Artificial Intelligence with language education in Vietnam: Opportunities and challenges					
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Parallel sessions						
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Room	Lecture Hall C	D.201	D.202	D.203	D.204	D.301
Moderator	Nguyen Van Dat, M.A	Dr. Nguyen Thi Chau Anh	Pham Ngoc Son, M.A	Dr. Nguyen Duc Chau	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Nguyen Ngoc Vu	Nguyen Thi Ngoc Tran, M.A
09.30 – 09.50	Difficulties in learning listening skill of non-English major students at Sai Gon University and suggested solutions to develop their listening autonomy Nguyen Thi Ha Nguyen Nu Nhu Linh	Anxiety and second language acquisition: How teachers deal with It Nguyen Thanh Hien	Integrating technology into the communicative language teaching approach to enhance effects of English Grammar teaching: a critical review and application Nguyen Van My	The implementation of ESA method in teaching grammar point of comparisons for con-Major HUFU students Nguyen Giang Huong	Video-based task teaching for non-English major students at HUFU Vo Thi Thu Thao	Applying shadowing technique and authentic materials to promote phonological awareness among young learners of English Nguyen Hong Oanh Nguyen Minh Tri

09.50 – 10.10	Making the IELTS more communicative, motivative and meaningful to EFL learners	An Investigation into first-year students' perceptions of learner autonomy through project-based learning	Using facebook as a tool to Improve writing skills for tertiary students	Bàn luận về ngữ nghĩa chỉ hướng trong trạng ngữ đa tầng tiếng Việt và tiếng Hán	An investigation of factors affects learning motivation of Business English majors in HUF1	Thành ngữ và tục ngữ Anh – Việt
	Nguyen Tran Nam Phuong	Nguyen Huu Ngoc	Tran Thi Trang Loan	Vo Thi Quynh Trang	Nguyen Thi Mai Huong	Truong Van Anh
10.10 – 10.30	Some effective strategies of teaching vocabulary	Analyzing difficulties of HUF1 students toward listening comprehension	Analysis Method of turn-taking signals to improve students' speaking skill	Difficulties In teaching speaking for English major students at Dak Lak College of Pedagogy and suggested solutions	The Effect of interactive white board on motivating Van Lang University's freshmen in lexical scquisition	Teaching reading skills by using techniques in a foreign language classroom
	Nguyen Thi Kim Anh	Ngo Thi Ngoc Hanh	Dang Thi Hong Nhung	Lu Thi Hai Yen	Le Huynh Ha Van	Duong Thi Bich Dao
10.30 – 10.40	Tea break (Lecture Hall Wings)					
10.40 – 11.20	Tran Tin Nghi, M.A. Dean of Faculty of Foreign languages, Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry Applying AI chatbot for teaching English Prepositions at tertiary level					
11.20 – 11.30	Rewarding and Closing Speech					

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